

Hybrid Provision of Energy based on Reliability and Resiliency by Integration of Dc Equipment

Work Package WP6
Swiss pilot

Deliverable D6.4
Design stability guidelines for hybrid AC-DC systems

Funding Instrument: Innovation Action
Call: H2020-LC-SC3-2020-EC-ES-SCC
Call Topic: LC-SC3-ES-10-2020 - DC – AC/DC hybrid grid for a modular, resilient and high RES share grid development

Project Start: 1 October 2020
Project Duration: 48 months

Beneficiary in Charge: EPFL

Document Identifier: doi:[10.5281/zenodo.7598022](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7598022)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	✓
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Deliverable Information

Document Administrative Information	
Project Acronym:	HYPERRIDE
Project Number:	957788
Deliverable Number:	D6.4
Deliverable Full Title:	Design stability guidelines for hybrid AC-DC systems
Deliverable Short Title:	Design stability guidelines for hybrid AC-DC systems
Document Identifier:	HYPERRIDE-D64-DesignStabilityGuidelinesForHybridACDCSystems-submitted
Beneficiary in Charge:	EPFL
Report Version:	v1.5
Contractual Date:	30/09/2024
Report Submission Date:	02/02/2023
Dissemination Level:	PU
Nature:	Report
Lead Author(s):	Drazen Dujic (EPFL)
Co-author(s):	Jules Mace, Renan Pillon Barcelos, Max Dupont and Andrea Cervone (EPFL)
Keywords:	Low Voltage ACDC microgrid, Active Front End, DC Transformer, PV Emulator, AC Grid Stability, European Union(EU), H2020, Project, HYPERRIDE, GA 957788
Status:	<input type="checkbox"/> draft, <input type="checkbox"/> final, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> submitted

Change Log

Date	Version	Author/Editor	Summary of Changes Made
30/09/2022	v1.0	Drazen Dujic, Jules Mace, Renan Pillon Barcelos, Max Dupont and Andrea Cervone (EPFL)	Draft report template
22/11/2022	v1.1	Tim Karsten (RWTH Aachen), Stefan Costea (Eaton)	Internal review
19/12/2022	v1.2	Jules Mace (EPFL)	Updated report
23/01/2023	v1.3	Gerhard Jambrich (AIT)	Coordinator Review
24/01/2023	v1.4	Jules Mace (EPFL)	Updated report
02/02/2023	v1.5	Gerhard Jambrich, Thomas Strasser (AIT)	Final version

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List of Abbreviations

EPFL	École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne
PEL	Power Electronics Laboratory
DESL	Distributed Electrical System Laboratory
DC	Direct Current
AC	Alternate Current
AFE	Active Front End
VSI	Voltage Source Inverter
DCT	DC Transformer
DAB	Dual Active Bridge
DMU	DC Measurement Unit
PV	Photovoltaic
MFT	Medium Frequency Transformer
PEBB	Power Electronics Building Block
DSP	Digital Signal Processor
FB	Full Bridge
SC	supercapacitor
PWM	Pulse Width Modulation
PLL	Phase-Locked Loop
DSOGI	Double Second Order Generalized Integrator
GCC	Grid Current Controller
DVC	DC Voltage Controller
SS	soft start
PRM	Power Reversal Method
MPPT	Maximum Power Point Tracking
ARW	Anti Reset Windup
DLPF	Digital Low Pass Filter
GNC	Generalized Nyquist Criterion
PRBS	Pseudo-Random Binary Sequence

Executive Summary

The HYPERRIDE project (HYbrid Provision of Energy based on Reliability and Resiliency via Integration of Dc Equipment) is a European project established under the H2020 call "LC-SC3-ES-10-2020 - DC - AC-DC hybrid grid for a modular, resilient and high RES share grid development". The project is aimed at exploring new infrastructure concepts, analyzing and enabling field implementations of DC and hybrid AC/DC grids.

Three pilot sites, located in Switzerland, Germany and Italy, have been chosen to cover different application focus areas.

The Swiss demonstrator realized at the École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL) is aimed at testing optimal control strategies for hybrid AC/DC grids, analyzing local/global stability properties and protection coordination, and explore adaptive reconfiguration approaches. To meet these goals, a hybrid low-voltage AC/DC microgrid has been realized as a joint cooperation between the Distributed Electrical System Laboratory (DESL) and the Power Electronics Laboratory (PEL) of EPFL.

This technical report describes the architecture, the functionalities and the commissioning of the main components of the microgrid realized by the Power Electronics Laboratory. These include AC/DC and DC/DC converters, which are respectively required for flexible interfacing the DC microgrid developed at PEL with the AC microgrid developed at DESL, and for allowing internal power flowing through different lines of the DC microgrid itself.

Due to significant efforts invested to realize and commission demonstrator infrastructure, original title of the report (deliverable) does not completely reflect what is actually presented here, as explained in subsequent sections. Complete demonstration of all developments will be reported in Deliverable D6.5.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This deliverable presents and reports the realization and testing of the main components of the microgrid realized for the Swiss demonstrator of the HYPERRIDE project by the Power Electronics Laboratory (PEL) of the École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL).

The main structures discussed in this report include the AC/DC converters for the interconnection of the Direct Current (DC) microgrid developed at PEL with the Alternate Current (AC) microgrid developed at the Distributed Electrical System Laboratory (DESL) in forerunner projects, some DC/DC converters to interface with one another different DC lines of the microgrid, and converters emulating the behaviour of a photovoltaic source connected to the DC grid. Realized infrastructure will be used for all subsequent investigation in the project.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows. Firstly, Section 2.1 briefly describes the architecture of the hybrid AC/DC microgrid realized at EPFL, and provides details about the demonstrator developed at PEL. Secondly, Section 3 reports the specifications, the parameters, the commissioning and the testing of the four Active Front End (AFE) units developed at PEL for the interconnection between the AC and the DC parts of the microgrid. Then, Section 4 describes the specifications, the parameters, the commissioning and the testing of the two DC Transformer (DCT) units developed at PEL to interconnect different DC lines of the microgrid with one another. Section 5 illustrates the realization and testing of the Photovoltaic (PV) emulators to be implemented in the DC microgrid. After that, in Section 6, some results of the overall DC microgrid testing are shown and discussed. Section 7 presents the current state of the analytical work regarding stability analysis of the microgrid. Finally, Section 8 recaps the conclusions of the work and reviews the future developments.

2 System Description

The aim of the Work Package 6 (WP06) of HYPERRIDE is to develop a laboratory setup of a hybrid low-voltage AC/DC microgrid, in a way to investigate performances, benefits and drawbacks of such kind of grid architecture, as well as developing guidelines for grid planning and operation, by testing optimal control strategies and adaptive reconfiguration approaches.

The swiss demonstrator at the École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL) is developed as a joint effort between the Distributed Electrical Systems Laboratory (DESL) and the Power Electronics Laboratory (PEL).

This section describes the architecture of the system and gives the specifications and parameters of the demonstrator developed at PEL.

2.1 AC/DC Microgrid Architecture

The architecture of the hybrid AC/DC microgrid realized at EPFL is depicted in Figure 1. Please note that DC part of the microgrid is continuously evolving and new conversion, protection and storage elements will be added throughout the project.

The microgrid is realised through the interconnection of an AC microgrid developed at DESL before the HYPERRIDE project (yellow subsystem in Figure 1) and of a DC microgrid developed at PEL during the HYPERRIDE project (blue subsystem in Figure 1).

The AC microgrid developed at DESL is a full-scale replica of the 15 nodes benchmark de-

Figure 1: Schematic architecture of the hybrid AC/DC microgrid developed at EPFL. The yellow subsystem represents the AC microgrid realised at DESL. The blue subsystem represents the DC microgrid realised at PEL. The interconnection between the AC and the DC microgrid is realized through four AFE units, also realized at PEL.

financed by the Task Force C6.04.02 of the Conseil International des Grands Réseaux Électriques (CIGRÉ). It is a three-phase low-voltage AC network working at a 50 Hz frequency with a rated line-to-line voltage of 400 V RMS. This microgrid is equipped with photovoltaic sources, a battery system supporting regulation in islanded scenarios, a supercapacitor-based storage system, a fuel cell system, an electrolyzer, a charging station for Electric Vehicles (EVs) and line and load emulators. Each node is equipped with a Phasor Measurement Unit (PMU), to provide the necessary feedback information to the supervisory grid controller.

The DC microgrid developed at PEL is composed of four DC lines, each of which is interfaced with a different node of the AC microgrid developed at DESL through an Active Front End (AFE). The four DC lines of the DC microgrid are also interfaced with each other through bidirectional DC/DC converters, to allow for power exchange among them. Two DC/DC converters are realized as DC Transformers (DCTs) based on series resonant conversion, and one DC/DC converter is realized as a Dual Active Bridge (DAB). Photovoltaic emulators are also included in the architecture of the DC microgrid, and are interfaced with the four DC lines to emulate a stochastic energy generation. Additionally, a supercapacitor-based storage system is also planned to be part of the DC microgrid. The DC side of the lines and the connection nodes of the DC/DC converters are equipped with DC Measurement Units (DC Measurement Units (DMUs)), which are also exploited to provide feedback to the supervisory grid controller.

2.2 Specifications

The laboratory demonstrator developed at PEL includes the DC microgrid and the four AFE units for the interconnection to the AC microgrid of DESL.

All the four DC lines have a rated voltage of 750 V, and are sized to exchange up to 45 kW with the AC microgrid through the corresponding AFE unit.

However, the voltage of the DC lines can be varied in the range [720 V; 780 V] in a way to generate a power flow through the DC/DC converters. This allows the supervisory grid controller to implement some optimal power and energy flow strategies within the hybrid AC/DC microgrid.

At the present state, the four AFE units and the two DCT units have been realized and commissioned. Four low-power PV emulators have been realized and tested, but they have not been included in the DC microgrid, yet. The DAB unit and the supercapacitor-based storage system are currently under development, with goals to include them into DC microgrid in early 2023.

The following sections describe in detail the commissioning and testing of the AFE units, of the DCT units, and of the PV emulators. It will then provide some preliminary results of the DC microgrid operation, obtained by connecting together the aforementioned units.

3 AC/DC Converter - Active Front End (AFE)

The Active Front End (AFE) converter is a key component of the analyzed hybrid microgrid, since it allows interfacing the AC side and the DC side providing a controllable and bidirectional power flow between them.

As described in Section 2.1, four identical AFE units have been developed to interface the AC microgrid developed at DESL with the DC microgrid developed at PEL. The purpose of each AFE is to regulate, at the same time, the reactive power injected into the AC line and the DC voltage of the DC line.

This section is aimed at describing the architecture, the hardware, the control and the features adopted in each AFE unit.

3.1 Architecture, Specifications and Parameters

The topology chosen for the AFE units is a two-level Voltage Source Inverter (VSI) with an LCL filter (see Figure 2). The converter ratings are presented in Table 1.

Figure 2: AFE structure with the power stage (top) and the control structure of the controller (bottom). The Power stage is based on a two-level VSI topology with an LCL filter. The control structure is based on a cascaded DC voltage regulation - AC current regulation structure.

The active-front end is based on a custom modified Hyundai N700 voltage source inverter (Hyundai N700 power stage hardware is kept, controller is exchanged with the LARA100 solution from Perun Technologies) and an LCL filter produced by Schaffner. A picture of those elements is presented in Figure 3. Other than the semiconductor devices, the N700 hardware also includes gate drivers, DC voltage and AC current sensors, a DC bus capacitance and a pre-charge circuit. The parameters of the passive elements are also presented in Table 1. Referring to the scheme in fig. 3b, the terminals [U,V,W] (i.e., inverter side of the N700 power hardware) are the three-phase terminals of the AFE (which are connected, through the LCL filter, to the AC grid), while [P,N] are the DC terminals. The terminals [R,S,T] (i.e., rectifier side

Table 1: Specifications and Parameters for the Active Front End (AFE) units.

Description	Symbol	Value
Rated power	$P_{AFE, rated}$	45 kVA
Rated AC voltage (RMS)	$V_{AC, rated}$	400 V
Rated AC current (RMS)	$I_{AC, rated}$	65 A
Rated AC grid frequency	f_g	50 Hz
Grid-Side Filtering Inductance	L_g	330 μ H
Converter-Side Filtering Inductance	L_c	740 μ H
Filtering Capacitance	C_f	100 μ F
Rated DC voltage	$V_{DC, rated}$	750 V
Rated DC Current	$I_{DC, rated}$	60 A
DC bus Capacitance	C_{DC}	705 μ F
Switching Frequency	f_{sw}	8 kHz

of the N700 power hardware) have only been used for testing and for the supply of auxiliary circuits.

Figure 3: Active Front End (AFE) converter elements - Power stage Hyundai N700 Module (a) Photo (b) Scheme (c) Schaffner FN6840 LCL Filter - Controller (d) LARA 100 suite of boards.

The control structure has been realized following a cascaded DC voltage regulation - AC grid

current regulation structure, with a Phase-Locked Loop (PLL) added to track the phase angle of the grid voltages, in order to control active and reactive powers separately. The control platform is based on the Digital Signal Processor (DSP) TMS320F28335 produced by Texas Instruments (TI). The DSP is interfaced to the power stage through the LARA 100 suite from Perun Technologies (please note that these LARA 100 elements were available at PEL, prior to HYPERRIDE project), which is shown in Figure 3d. This is a set of boards interfacing the DSP, the inverter, external analog and digital inputs and outputs as well as communication and voltage measurements. The suite also includes various protection features and it can be interfaced to a host PC through a proprietary software Perun PowerDesk, allowing to control and monitor the code deployed in the TI DSP.

The converter power stage and controller are integrated into a cabinet, that also includes ac and dc contactors, ac circuit breakers and other monitoring and protection circuitry required to have a complete safe and operable converter module. The cabinet is shown in Figure 4.

3.2 Controller Architecture and Commissioning

As previously mentioned, the control architecture is a conventional cascaded DC voltage regulation - AC grid current regulation structure with a Phase-Locked Loop (PLL). The AC/DC converter in the grid, together with a detailed control diagram, is presented in the Figure 5.

The TI TMS320F28335 controller has been programmed using the functionality of both the TI C2000 Code Generation features of PLECS, and of the low-level C/C++ programming options of TI Code Composer Studio (CCS).

The AFE operation is controlled by a state machine implemented at the DSP level, and safety protections are implemented at the cabinet level (through the circuit breakers), at the controller hardware level (through the LARA 100 analog protection system) and at the software level (based on analog current and voltage readings, trip zone reading and state machine). At each level, the contactors can be disconnected and the PWM signals can be interrupted.

Regarding the commissioning of the controller (control performance and protection capabilities), a two step process, illustrated in Figure 6, has been employed. Firstly, the controller is tested in simulation offline using a PLECS model of the controller, the power stage (inverter and filter) and grid. Once the controller model has been validated, it is translated into C code using PLECS Coder, then compiled using TI's Code Composer Studio and finally flashed in the DSP. So, the same controller is employed in simulation and experiments. The environment (microgrid lines connected to the AFE) has been physically emulated using various lab equipment. The used equipment include a 41 kW ac load from Junxy Energy (shown in Figure 7a), and a Regatron TC.ACS grid emulator (shown in Figure 7b).

Next subsections provide a detailed explanation of the structure, the tuning and the testing of each section of the AFE control algorithm.

3.2.1 Reference Frame Transformations

The three-phase ac variables have been used in the controller both in the stationary $\alpha\beta$ reference frame and in the synchronous dq reference frame (synchronised with the phase angle of the ac grid voltages). The amplitude invariant Clarke's and Park's transformations have been used to express three-phase voltage and current components in different reference frames:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_\alpha \\ x_\beta \\ x_0 \end{bmatrix} = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} x_A \\ x_B \\ x_C \end{bmatrix} \iff \begin{bmatrix} x_A \\ x_B \\ x_C \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 \\ -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & 1 \\ -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} x_\alpha \\ x_\beta \\ x_0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_d \\ x_q \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) & \sin(\theta) \\ -\sin(\theta) & \cos(\theta) \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} x_\alpha \\ x_\beta \end{bmatrix} \iff \begin{bmatrix} x_\alpha \\ x_\beta \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) & -\sin(\theta) \\ \sin(\theta) & \cos(\theta) \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} x_d \\ x_q \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 4: AFE converter cabinet - composed in the front of the power stage (inverter and LCL filter) and controller and in the back of the interface and protection elements: AC and DC contactors, AC circuit breakers, light tower control, etc.

3.2.2 Phase-Locked Loop (PLL) - Controller, gain tuning and experimental validation

In order to be connected to the grid, the AC voltages generated by the active front end $v_{c,ABC}$ need to be synchronised to the AC voltages $v_{g,abc}$ of the grid. Indeed, for a grid-connected converter, the knowledge of the instantaneous phase angle of the grid voltages is required by the reference frame transformations from the stationary to the synchronous reference frame, and allows a decoupled control of the active and reactive power absorbed by the AFE. This task can be accomplished through a Phase-Locked Loop (PLL) algorithm.

However, as a microgrid is prone to grid unbalances, the grid voltages may not constitute a three-phase symmetrical set of sinusoidal waveforms. Therefore, the PLL also has to cope with such voltage unbalances. To do so, a Double Second Order Generalized Integrator (DSOGI) phase-locked loop (DSOGI-PLL) has been developed. The structure is presented in Figure 8. This scheme allows the extraction in real-time of the positive sequence and negative sequence of the three-phase grid voltage system, and the synchronization with the instantaneous phase angle of only the positive sequence. This way, any voltage unbalance of the ac grid is neutralized and does not affect the desired synchronization.

Referring to Figure 8b, the gain k of the DSOGI has been set as $\sqrt{2}$. The gains of the PI controller of the PLL scheme represented in Figure 8c have been tuned as in Table 2.

To validate the gain tuning and the performance of the PLL in time, three tests are here reported: a frequency step and a grid voltage step to validate the PLL, and a voltage step of only

Figure 5: Active Front End (AFE) converter in the grid with detailed control structure. The DC voltage controller is regulating the DC voltage by adjusting the AC power - or d-axis current, the AC current controller is regulating the AC currents in the $\alpha\beta$ frame by adjusting the modulation voltage reference v_c^{REF} .

Figure 6: Controller Design Workflow, from offline simulations in PLECS to experimental validation.

Figure 7: Lab equipment for AFE commissioning (a) 400V 41kVA RL Load by Junxy Energy (b) Regatron TC ACS Grid Emulator.

one line (here $V_{g,a}$) to validate the DSOGI performances towards an unbalanced grid condition. The responses are presented in Figure 9, including a comparison between simulation and experimental results. The experimental tests have been executed by connecting the AC terminals of the AFE to a Regatron TC.ACS grid emulator, allowing complete control over the voltages $v_{g,ABC}$ at the AFE terminals.

As can be noted, the simulation and experimental results are very similar in shape and in time. The response to a frequency step of 5 Hz is 120 ms. The response to a voltage amplitude step

Figure 8: Phase-Locked Loop (PLL) controller scheme (a) Global structure (b) DSOGI structure (c) PLL structure.

Table 2: AFE Phase-Locked Loop (PLL) gains.

Gain	Formula	Value
$t_{settling\ time}$		200 ms
ζ_{PLL}		$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$
$K_{P,PLL}$	$\frac{9.2}{\zeta_{PLL}}$	92
$K_{I,PLL}$	$\frac{21.16}{t_{settling\ time}^2 \cdot \zeta_{PLL}^2}$	1058

of 41 V lasts less than 10 ms, similarly to the response of the PLL following a voltage amplitude step of 36.5 V on the phase a.

Figure 9: PLL tuning validations:
 Frequency step from 45 to 50Hz (a) Simulation (b) Experiments
 Voltage amplitude step from 284 to 327V (c) Simulation (d) Experiments
 Phase a voltage amplitude step from 327 to 290.5V (e) Simulation (f) Experiments.

3.2.3 Pulse Width Modulation (PWM)

The switching signals for the semiconductor devices have been generated through a standard Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) algorithm exploiting a modulating signal - carrier comparison, implemented through the available peripherals of the TI TMS320F28335 DSP.

The carrier frequency has been set to 8 kHz, and a single-update mode has been implemented to set the duty-cycles d_{ABC} of the three AFE legs. A 3 μ s dead-time has been implemented to allow a safe switching of the complementary semiconductor devices of each AFE leg.

A min/max common mode injection has been used to generate the duty-cycles d_{ABC} from the

knowledge of the voltage references $v_{c,ABC}^{REF}$ and of the measured DC-bus voltage v_{dc} , improving the DC-bus voltage utilisation.

3.2.4 AC Grid Current Control (GCC) - Controller, gain tuning and experimental validation

The AC Grid Current Controller (GCC) has been implemented following the scheme represented in Figure 10. It is controlling the currents in the $\alpha\beta$ frame with a proportional resonant (PR) controller for each axis, while the grid voltage $v_{g,\alpha\beta n}$ has been used as a feed-forward term.

Figure 10: AC grid current controller (a) Full model (b) Proportional-Resonant (PR) controller.

The controller gains have been tuned according to formulas presented in Table 3.

Table 3: AFE AC Grid Current Controller (GCC) gain tuning

Gain	Formula	Value
K_{CC}	$\omega_{cc} = \frac{1}{3T_{SW}}$	2667
$k_{P,CC}$	$L \approx L_1 + L_2$	$0.900 \cdot 10^{-3}$
$k_{R,CC}$	$R \approx R_{L1} + R_{L2}$	0.100

The controller has been tested by connecting the AC terminals of the AFE to the Regatron TC.ACS grid emulator, and by performing step change in the reference quadrature axis current $i_{c,q}^{REF}$. By only varying the quadrature axis current $i_{c,q}^{REF}$, the reactive power Q absorbed by the AFE can be changed without altering the active power flowing through the converter itself. The test results are shown in Figure 11). As it is shown, the response is fast and the responses in simulation and in the experiments are well matching.

3.2.5 DC Voltage Control (DVC) - Controller, gain tuning and experimental validation

The DC voltage regulator has been implemented following the scheme represented in Figure 12. The squared reference and measured DC voltages V_{dc} and V_{dc}^{REF} are compared and their difference is the input of a Proportional-Integral (PI) regulator, tuned so that the dc voltage regulator dynamics are much slower than the grid current regulator dynamics. The output of the PI controller is the reference direct axis current component $i_{c,d}^{REF}$ to be imposed by the GCC. In addition, in order to prevent extensive voltage ripples, the voltage reference is conditioned through a rate limiter. The controller gain values are presented in Table 4.

Figure 11: Validation of the GCC, tested with a q -axis current reference step change from 0 to $i_{c,q}^{REF} = 30$ A, corresponding to a Reactive Power step change from 0 to $Q = 14.6$ kVAr. (a) Simulation (b) Experiments.

Figure 12: DVC scheme.

Table 4: AFE DVC gain tuning.

K_{DVC}	$\frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{C_{DC}}{\frac{3}{2} V_{gd}} \cdot \frac{1}{60 T_{sw}}$	$0.722 \cdot 10^{-6}$
$k_{P,DVC}$	1	1
$k_{I,DVC}$	$\frac{1}{16 T_{sw}}$	16.7
ramp slope		200 V s^{-1}

The validation of the controller is presented in Figure 13, considering a reference voltage change of 50 V (i.e., from an initial value of 750 V) to a final value of 750 V. The reference reactive power has been kept to zero. The experimental tests have been executed connecting the AC terminals of the AFE to the Regatron TC.ACS grid emulator, while the DC bus of the AFE has been kept unloaded. Again, for both simulations and experiments, the curves are very similar, showing the accuracy of the simulation model. The response to the 50 V voltage reference change is of around 400 ms, taking into account the 200 V s^{-1} ramp slope imposed by the rate limiter.

Figure 13: V_{dc} step (a) Simulation (b) Experiments.

4 Direct Current Transformers

The bidirectional resonant DC transformer is the element designed to allow the voltage adaptation and interconnection between two different dc buses. This converter is called DC Transformer (DCT), relating its functionality to the well-know ac transformer - an equipment allowing the voltage adaptation, and adjusting the power flow naturally. This section describes the works done around this converters and demonstrate its operation principles when connected to the DC microgrid.

4.1 Technology Description

The ultimate goal of a DCT is purely to connect two DC buses, allowing the power exchange between them. The concept assumes that there is no closed-control loop for this converter: thus, when the DCT is connected into the DC grid, the power exchange between the DC buses is given by the natural power flow of the system (Barcelos & Dujčić, 2022). In this sense, the main desired characteristics of a DCT are:

- High efficiency;
- Simplicity;
- Bulk power processing (not a modular converter);
- No closed-loop control;
- Robustness;
- Load independent behaviour;
- Bidirectional power flow capabilities;
- Isolation at high frequency.

The DCT selected in this project is based on the LLC topology, taking the advantage of the stable open loop operation when operating close to the resonant frequency, of its high efficiency and of the stiff voltage-ratio loading characteristics (Barcelos & Dujčić, 2021). Figure 14(a) shows the circuitual topology of an LLC-based DCT, employing Full Bridge (FB) power stages on both the primary and secondary side. Figure 14(b) shows, side-by-side, the two DCT prototypes developed in the lab. Both DCTs have the same ratings, and both are tested and evaluated as described in this report.

The power stages connected on each DC port can operate individually, and do not require any synchronisation or signal feedback between them. This means that, while one side is switching, the other side can operate as a passive rectifier, thus requiring only one PWM reference for the DCT. When the power flow reverses, the power stages switch their roles, and redirect the currents to the other side. Hence, to allow a bidirectional operation, the resonant converter requires a minimum of intelligence to identify where to direct the power.

Besides that, the DCT has other features as:

- The *idle mode*, where the DCT stays in standby when there is no load (so no power to be transmitted);
- The *soft-start*, to promote a smooth transition in the initialization process and in power transitions.

Figure 14: (a) Direct Current Transformer topology, and in (b) photo of the two DCTs prototypes developed in the lab.

4.2 Hardware testing

The DCT was built with a three phase Voltage Source Inverter (VSI) developed in the lab, with two legs operated to create the FB. The switches are 1.7 kV IGBTs from Infineon (SKM 400GB176D). The resonant tank consists of a 100 kW Medium Frequency Transformer (MFT) with integrated resonant capacitors, developed in (Mogorovic & Dujic, 2019).

The complete schematic of the DCT, with a description of the controllers and of the test setup, is illustrated in Figure 15. This setup was used to verify the DCT functionality and test the basic functions before connecting it to the DC microgrid. The DCTs parameters are described in Table 5.

Figure 15: Schematic of the complete system. The two DC buses are created with voltage sources. Detailed measurements correspond to the actual measurements for the experimental waveforms. For the test setup system, controller, relays, and power sources are accessed through PC.

Table 5: Specifications and Parameters for the DC Transformer (DCT) units.

Description	Symbol (Unit)	Value (DCT 1)	Value (DCT 2)
Rated power	P_{dc}	100 kW	100 kW
Rated DC voltage - Primary Side	$V_{dc,1}$	750 V	750 V
Rated DC voltage - Secondary Side	$V_{dc,2}$	750 V	750 V
Switching frequency	f_{sw} (kHz)	10 kHz	10 kHz
Leakage inductance	L_r	11.6 μ H	9.5 μ H
Magnetizing inductance	L_m	750 μ H	1100 μ H
Resonant capacitance	C_r	37.5 μ F	37.5 μ F
DC bus capacitance - Primary Side	$C_{dc,1}$	1020 μ F	1020 μ F
DC bus capacitance - Secondary Side	$C_{dc,2}$	1020 μ F	1020 μ F
Pre-charging resistance - Primary Side	$R_{pre,1}$	10 Ω	10 Ω
Pre-charging resistance - Secondary Side	$R_{pre,2}$	10 Ω	10 Ω

4.2.1 Prototype construction

The Power Electronics Building Blocks (PEBBs) were built, attached to the panel, and the measurements and control units were wired with the distribution panel on the back. Figure 16 shows some photos of the process.

The front panel of the DCT hosts the two power stages and the resistors for the pre-charging circuit. On the back panel there are the relays and current and voltage sensors (on the top), the Combi-IO and PECMI boards (in the middle) and the auxiliary power supplies and the AC 800PEC control board (on the bottom). The MFT is placed on the table. And in the last photo, the complete DCT.

4.3 Demonstration, Characteristics, and Features

The experimental setup consists in two DC buses, energized with two switched power amplifier - TC.ACS from Regatron. The DCT is controlled by the ABB's AC 800PEC, and the schematic and experimental prototype are shown in Fig. 15 and 14(b), respectively. Thus, to simulate any load variation, the voltages of the two DC buses are actively controlled in order to provoke various power flows.

4.3.1 Pre-charging circuit

The pre-charging is performed by inserting charging resistors in the current path of each DC bus, in a way that it is charged through the resistor, thus limiting the current overshoot during the start-up of the system. The resistors are then bypassed once the pre-charging operation is complete.

By referring to Figure 17, the pre-charging sequence is done by the following logic:

1. Close resistor relay (Relay 3) + Close DC^- relay (Relay 2);
2. Open resistor relay (Relay 3) + Close DC^+ relay (Relay 1).

The pre-charging sequence is activated only when there is voltage on the DCT terminals (i.e.,

Figure 16: Photos of the construction of the DCT. (a) PEBB; (b) DCT in the panel; (c) Distribution panel; (d) Complete distribution panel; (e) Protection plexiglass; (f) Complete DCT.

Figure 17: DC link pre-charging circuit scheme.

$v_{dc,1}$ in Figure 17) and the voltage on the DC bus capacitor (i.e., $u_{dc,1}$ in Figure 17) is below a chosen threshold.

Figure 18: Illustration of the PWM initialization sequence, and zoom in the three-level voltage in the resonant tank after power reversal. c_1 is PWM carrier, m_1 and m_2 are modulation index for leg 1 and leg 2 respectively. s_x is the gate signal of device x , and V_{ab} is resonant tank voltage. After power reversal detection, DCT is turned-off for two switching periods, and starts the initialization sequence with soft-start.

4.3.2 Soft-start

At the first moment, the DCT starts with a soft start (SS) strategy, to promote a smooth initialization. Indeed, during the initialization stage (i.e. every start or reversal of power), the DCT should not receive the full square wave in the resonant tank, which is fully discharged, because this could cause a very high inrush current that could damage the hardware components (Kucka & Dujic, 2021a).

Here, the soft-start is performed by increasing the duty cycle from 0% to 50% slowly. Figure 18 shows the working principle of the adopted soft-start strategy.

Besides that, a variable soft-start time duration has been implemented accordingly to the power demand. Thus, by using DC voltages, the speed of the soft-start can be determined by the rate of change of the voltage difference ($\Delta V'_{dct} = d\Delta V_{dct}/dt$, with $\Delta V_{dct} = V_{dc,1} - V_{dc,2}$ denoting the voltage difference between the primary and secondary side of the DCT).

To demonstrate the different dynamics for different soft-start speed, Figure 19(a) shows an experimental results for the soft-start with three different speeds. Thus, the duration of the soft-start becomes a parameter, where depending on the load dynamics, the initialization of the DCT is set accordingly.

4.3.3 DCT Operation

For all the experiments, the DC bus 1 was regulated to $V_{dc,1} = 750$ V during all the time, while DC bus 2 varies following the emulated load dynamic. Therefore, in order to provoke a power flow around $P_{dc} \approx 20$ kW, the DC bus 2 is set to $V_{dc,2} = 742$ V. Figure 19(b) shows the experimental results for the resonant currents and voltages. It can be notice from this test that the turn-off current of DCT is around 16 A, and the converter is operating below the resonant frequency.

Figure 19: (a) Experimental waveforms showing the soft-start of From the top to the bottom, the soft-start duration is: 0.14 s, 0.08 s and 0.014 s; (b) Experimental waveforms showing the DCT operation at 20 kW.

4.3.4 Power Reversal Methods

According to the operating condition of the microgrid, the DCT power can either flow from the primary side to the secondary side, or vice versa. The Power Reversal Method (PRM) is the criterion that determines the active power stage of DCT, and that is responsible for changing the active power stage in case of power flow reversal (Kucka & Dujic, 2021b).

Essentially, the method reads current and/or voltages to determine what is the power flow direction. Thus, different methods were developed in order to identify a power transition .

Figure 20 illustrates the logic flow-chart of the developed methods. Their working principle is described in the following.

The first method (named PRM-1) is based on the DC currents direction, and follows the flow-chart of Figure 20(a). For this method, one or both currents can be used to determine the power reversal. The method will detect the change once one or both DC currents crosses zero and change its polarity. This method was tested and the experimental results are shown in Figure 21, with zoom in each transition.

The second method (named PRM-2) is based on the DC current rate of change, and follows the flow-chart of Figure 20(b). This method can be considered as a lead indicator, where as soon as the DC current is below the defined threshold, it does not wait for the zero crossing to command the power reversal. Essentially, this method is monitoring the rate of change of dc current (di/dt), and in low range of values of current, it triggers the power reversal if the derivative is going in the opposite direction than the current signal. Thus, this method can anticipate the power reversal, and this can be beneficial for the very fast transition dynamics.

The third method (named PRM-3) is based on the DC voltages to estimate the power flow

Figure 20: Flow chart of the PRMs. (a) PRM-1, based on the DC currents; (b) PRM-2, based on the DC current rate of change; (c) PRM-3, based on the DC voltages. All the PRMs run indefinitely with DCT's operation. Side 1 or 2 means power stage 1 or 2, relating to the DC port.

Figure 21: Experimental waveforms showing the response of the DCT for the slow reverse of power flow. This experiment use a PRM based in DC currents (PRM-1) to detect the power reversal, and the load is performed with a ramp in the DC bus 2 - ($V_{dc,2} = 740 \text{ V}$ to $V_{dc,2} = 755 \text{ V}$) - while DC bus 1 is kept constant ($V_{dc,1} = 750 \text{ V}$). In (a) the complete power reversal transition; in (b) the operation waveforms for the forward mode; in (c) the power reversal transition, with details on the idle period of DCT and soft start sequence with three level waveform in the resonant tank (V_{ab}); in (d) operation waveforms for the backward mode.

Figure 22: Experimental waveforms showing the response of the DCT for the step reverse, using the (a) PRM-2, based on the DC current rate of change, and (b) PRM-3, based on DC voltages. Direction of the currents correspond to the schematic of the system. Zoom shows the moment of the power reversal, where it is possible to note that DCT enters in idle mode and starts its initialisation sequence with a three-level waveform. Before the method detect the power reversal, the DCT stays during a period of time with only the magnetising current noticeable in the third plot in blue. During the IdM, a resonance to equalise the voltages over switches occur in the resonant tank.

direction, and follows the flow-chart of Figure 20(c). It identifies by acknowledging which DC port voltage is higher/lower than the other. The threshold of this method is defined by the DCT losses. This solution, differently from DC currents methods, will identify the power reversal only after the DC current crossing zero. Each of these methods have a threshold band to around zero to avoid jittering during slow power reversals.

Figures 22 and 23 show the results for the step change and ramp change for the power reversal using the PRM-2 and PRM-3. For the step change both methods has similar performance. However, it is noticeable that the method based on voltages takes more time to identify the power reversal for the ramp load change. This is visible in the amount of time only magnetizing current was circulating in the resonant tank (blue curve in the third graph).

In the end, all three methods worked properly, and they will be used in the DCT.

Using the developed PRMs, the DCT still operates in open loop, which is one of its most important features. This makes its implementation in DC grid easy, since the DCT acts as a device only allowing the voltage adaptation and interfacing two DC buses, without controlling power or voltage on its terminals.

4.3.5 Idle Mode

The idle mode of DCT can be used to determine its operation limits, by setting a voltage/power threshold to let the DCT operate. In this case, the DCT will drive the current only when the power flow is well defined and enough current will flow throughout its ports. This feature allows reducing the losses of the DCT by avoiding unnecessary power consumption due to magnetizing current in no load condition.

Figure 23: Experimental waveforms showing the response of the DCT for the slow reverse, using the (a) PRM-2, based on the DC current rate of change, and (b) PRM-3, based on DC voltages. Zoom shows the moment of the power reversal, where it is possible to note that DCT enters in idle mode and starts its initialisation sequence with a three-level waveform. It is noticeable from third plot that the PRM-3 detected the power reversal later.

In the adopted solution, when the power being processed by the DCT is below a chosen threshold P_{th} , the DCT stops switching, with the aim of improving the efficiency.

The duration of the idle mode is determined by the dynamics of the voltages on the two DCbuses: indeed, to leave this mode, the voltage difference $\Delta V_{dct} = v_{dc,1} - v_{dc,2}$ must be higher than a defined threshold ΔV_{dct}^{th} .

Moreover, the slew-rate of the voltage difference sets the soft-start duration, by acknowledging if the time derivative $\Delta V'_{dct} = d(\Delta V_{dct})/dt$ is bigger than a defined threshold. This case is also illustrated in Figure 24, where, depending on the $\Delta V'_{dct}$, the initialization of the DCT can be with a slow soft-start, or a fast soft-start, matching the dynamics of the system.

Figure 24: Illustration of the Idle Mode operation principle. The DCT is initialized only when the ΔV_{dct} overcomes ΔV_{dct}^{th} . In case the voltage variation is too aggressive, the soft-start period is reduced. At the moment the power being processed by DCT is below a P_{th} , the DCT stops switching, improving the efficiency.

Figure 25: Experimental waveforms showing the DCT in No-load idle mode, with a power threshold. During the shared period, DCT is in idle state waiting for the expected power to overcome its threshold. At $t = 0$ s the DCT turns on by noticing the DC voltages mismatch. Then, once the DC buses return to equilibrium, at $t = 3.5$ s, the DCT turns off, as the power is below the threshold value. In (a) the waveforms for the DCT operation; in (b) details on the soft start sequence when the DCT notice the need to turn on and transfer power; in (c) the steady-state operation waveforms; and in (d) details on the turn off moment, when the DCT is not required anymore and was only consuming magnetizing current, creating unnecessary losses.

Figure 25 shows the experimental results for the idle mode operation. The DCT operates as expected by turning ON only when the voltage difference between the two DC buses overcomes a certain threshold (in this case, imposed to 5 V), and turns OFF when the DCT is processing only the magnetizing current, thus increasing its efficiency. In this experiment is also possible to note the soft-start when the DCT is initialized.

4.3.6 Complete test

After validating each single operation and feature of the DCT, a long and complete test profile has been executed to check its proper functioning. In this way, the complete test consist in emulating what can happen when the DCT is connected to the DC microgrid. The experimental test has been executed as follows.

The complete operation of DCT is shown in Figures 26, 27, and 28. Figures 27, and 28 are zoom-in of the big overview result.

In this experiment, at $t = -3.5$ s (time relative to half of the total times) the DCT was in forward operating, when after $t = -3.5$ s load can suddenly change, and the power flow reverses. At this moment, the DCT recognised that the power dropped and set the DCT to idle mode. However, as the transition was fast, the DCT initialised fast, following the load demand, as it can be seen in Fig. 27.

In a second moment, the DCT is operating in a backward configuration, when after $t = 1.5$ s the load starts decreasing again, bot now slowly. After reach a certain level, the DCT is turned off to increase the efficiency, once the power been processed is too low.

The DCT stays in idle mode for a while, when after $t = 3.5$ s, the load is demanding power, but slowly, what makes the DCT turn-on slowly. To turn the DCT on, the voltage difference between its terminals were above the threshold, indicating that there is enough power to be transmitted

Figure 26: Experimental waveforms showing the response of the DCT for a fast power reverse, and slow power reversal. The DCT uses PRA to determine its operation limits and set the proper initialization time. Direction of the currents correspond to the schematic of the system. The DCT process power in both directions and a load profile is performed to test and validate the PRA. Squares mark the zoom available in Figures 27 and 28.

Figure 27: Experimental waveforms showing the response of the DCT for the fast power reversal (Zoom-in in the first transition of Fig. 26.) In (a) the moment DCT enters in Idle Mode by reducing the processed power below the threshold. Zoom-in in the moment DCT goes idle. In (b) the moment DCT starts the soft-start with fast dynamic load. Zoom-in the in the moment the power stage start switching.

and the DCT should provide the path.

In the end, the DCT operated as expected and was able to follow the natural power flow according to the DC voltages. After this experiment the DCT is ready to be integrated into the DC microgrid.

Figure 28: Experimental waveforms showing the response of the DCT for the slow power reversal (Zoom-in in the second and third transition of Fig. 26.) In (a) the moment DCT enters in Idle Mode by reducing the processed power below the threshold. Zoom-in in the moment DCT goes idle. In (b) the moment DCT starts the soft-start with slow dynamic load. Zoom-in the in the moment the power stage start switching.

5 Photovoltaic (PV) Emulator

In this document, what is referred to as a PV emulator consists of the converter emulating the actual photovoltaic panel or string of panels as well as the DC/DC converter necessary to interface it with the DC lines.

As described in Section 2.1, a PV emulator is to be connected to each of the four DC lines, providing stochastic generation emulation capabilities. This section aims at describing the architecture, hardware and control of the PV emulators.

5.1 Hardware and topology

The PV emulators have been realised using the Power Electronics Teaching Setup (PETS) developed at the PEL (Figure 29), which integrates most of the hardware required for it.

Similarly to AFEs presented in section 3, each PETS is based on Hyundai N700 frequency inverters, equipped with the LARA-100 platform from PERUN Technologies, interfacing each power stage with a Texas Instruments TMS320F28335 DSP.

Additionally, the PETS is equipped with passive components, in particular three DC inductors used for DC/DC power conversion, and a Delta Elektronika SM660-AR-11 power supply capable of emulating PV panels.

The parameters relevant to the use of PETS as PV emulators are listed in table 6.

Most of the components terminal can be accessed through the front panel of the PETS, allowing easy re-configuration of the connections of the teaching setup to demonstrate various power electronics topologies.

Figure 30 illustrates the topology and front panel configuration used for the PV emulator. The PV source is emulated by the Delta Elektronika power supply and the three DC inductors are used together with the two-level three-phase voltage source inverter of the power stage to form a DC/DC interleaved Boost converter. The braking chopper is used as a load for standalone testing of the PV emulator.

For connecting of the emulator to the DC grid, a pre-charge circuit is needed to reduce the inrush current in C_{DC} . A circuit similar to the one described in section 4.3.1 is currently being developed.

Figure 29: Power Electronics Teaching Setup.

Table 6: Electrical parameters of the parts of the PETS used for the PV emulators.

PV panel emulator			Passives				Power stage		
P_{MAX}	V_{MAX}	C_{PV}	R_{DC}	L_{DC}	C_{DC}	R_{BR}	P_{MAX}	$f_{SW,MAX}$	$V_{DC,MAX}$
3.6 kW	660 V	56 μ F	382 m Ω	33 mH	705 μ F	240 Ω	5.5 kW	11 kHz	750 V

Figure 30: Configuration of the PETS for the PV emulator.

5.2 Control architecture and tuning

5.2.1 Overview

As illustrated in Figure 31, the control scheme adopted is a classical cascaded control with perturb and observe (P&O) Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT).

At the heart of this scheme, three current control loops are found. Each one controls the average current of one of the three Boost inductors. This ensures that the total current is equally shared between the three legs of the converter. Then, the upper control loop uses the controlled inductor currents to adjust the charge level of the input capacitance, effectively controlling the voltage of the PV string. Finally, the MPPT algorithm adjusts the set point for the input voltage controller in order to operate the PV panel at its maximum power point.

For the discrete time implementation of these controllers, the sampling frequency is equal to the switching frequency (here, $f_s = f_{sw} = 10$ kHz).

Figure 31: Interleaved Boost converter control scheme. Each branch of the converter is associated with a current control loop, a single voltage controller generates the current set-points and the voltage set-point is generated by the MPPT algorithm.

5.2.2 Current control

Figure 32: Current control loop, it consists of a PI controller with stop integration ARW and PV voltage feedforward. In the circuit box, the subtraction junction represents that the voltage across the inductor is the difference between the PV voltage and the voltage of the semiconductor term. A measurement of the PV voltage is also used on the control side as a feedforward term.

Figure 32 illustrates the current control in more details. The current of each inductor is controlled by a Proportional Integral (PI) regulator tuned using the magnitude optimum criterion (Umland & Safiuddin, 1990) with stop integration Anti Reset Windup (ARW) and feedforward of the PV string voltage.

The controller design was done in continuous-time domain, but the implementation on the DSP is discrete-time. The backward Euler approximation was used and the PI coefficients, expressed as a function of circuit variables, are:

$$K_p = \frac{L_{DC}}{3T_{SW}} = 110 \quad K_i = \frac{R_{DC}}{L_{DC}} T_{SW} = 1.158 \cdot 10^{-3} \quad (1)$$

5.2.3 Voltage control

The full voltage control scheme is illustrated in fig. 33, it is also based on a PI controller with stop integration ARW. The output of the voltage controller is a reference for the current control loops, this reference is equally shared between all three current controllers. In this way, the stress is shared between the three branches of the converter.

Because the plant controlled by this voltage regulator can be approximated by a pure integrator, the symmetrical optimum criterion (Umland & Safiuddin, 1990) is used for tuning. This tuning method introduces an overshoot in the tracking step response, which is compensated by the addition of a Digital Low Pass Filter (DLPF) at the input of the controller.

Figure 33: Voltage control loop. The output of the voltage controller is a current reference which is shared between the three branches of the interleaved Boost converter.

Again, the control design was done in the continuous-time domain, but the implementation on the DSP is discrete-time. The backward Euler approximation is used and the PI coefficients found with the symmetrical optimum criterion are expressed as:

$$K_p = \frac{C_{PV}}{2T_\Sigma} = 6 \cdot 10^{-2} \quad K_i = \frac{T_{s,V}}{4T_\Sigma} = 5.357 \cdot 10^{-2} \quad (2)$$

Where $T_{s,V}$ is the sampling period (100 μ s) and T_Σ is a sum of delays equal to 466.7 μ s in this application.

5.2.4 Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithm

For MPPT, the perturb and observe (P&O) algorithm (Esram & Chapman, 2007) is used (Figure 34). The operating principle of this algorithm is simple and straightforward. It consists of incrementing the PV voltage reference, then measuring the PV output power, if it is higher than at the previous time step, the voltage reference is incremented again. This goes on until the power decreases with respect to the previous sample. At this point, the PV voltage reference is decremented. Now the algorithm decrements the voltage reference until the power decreases, at which point the voltage is incremented again, etc. Eventually, the system ends up oscillating close to the maximum power point.

In the PETS, the PV panel current is not measured. Therefore, the PV power is approximated as $P_{PV} \approx I_{Boost} \cdot V_{PV}$ (where I_{Boost} is the sum of the three inductors currents). This is a good approximation as the sampling frequency chosen for MPPT here is 100 Hz and the inner control loops are much faster. This leaves enough time for the voltage and current control loops to settle between updates of the voltage reference by the MPPT algorithm. Therefore, $I_{PV} = I_{Boost}$ is true at the time instants for which the power is sampled.

The MPPT algorithm has been empirically tuned, and voltage increments of 5 V have been used.

Figure 34: Perturb and Observe MPPT algorithm.

5.3 Test and validation

The described PV emulator has been tested experimentally in a standalone configuration.

Figure 35 shows the graphical interface of the Delta power supply, loaded with test settings for a dynamical simulation in which a string of PV panels is simulated for a cyclic irradiance profile.

The proper functioning of the DC/DC converter and the maximum power point tracking algorithm are shown in Figure 36. In Figure 36a, on the top row, it can be observed that the

converter follows the maximum power correctly. The second and third rows show that the measured voltage and currents closely match their set-points. Figure 36b is showing the operating point of the emulated PV panels on a power-voltage graph, for reference, P-V characteristics of the simulated panels for the minimum and maximum irradiance are also displayed. It is clear that the operating point oscillates about the maximum power point, the oscillations are due to the working principle of the perturb and observe algorithm as well as measurement noise.

Figure 35: Delta elektronika interface for dynamic PV emulations. Parameters of the PV panel and irradiance over time are specified in the bottom left side. The right side shows the panel characteristic curves for the minimum and maximum simulated irradiances.

Figure 36: Experimental validation of the PV emulators: (a) measurements of power, voltage and currents vs time for a dynamical irradiance profile, (b) power vs voltage trajectory during the same testing scenario as in (a).

6 DC Microgrid Testing

In this section, the DC microgrid operation is presented and discussed.

Firstly, the demonstration of operation of one DCT in the DC microgrid is presented, considering two separate DC bus lines separately controlled by the AFE units. Secondly, a demonstration of the simultaneous operation of two DCTs connected to three DC buses is shown.

6.1 Demonstration of the DCT operating in the dc microgrid

For the first tests, one DCT has been connected to two DC buses, each of which being voltage-regulated by one AFE as presented in Figure 37. Two configurations are proposed to evaluate the operation of the two DCTs presented in Section 4:

- in the first configuration Figure 37a, the DCT1 is connected to buses 2 and 3, regulated respectively by AFE2 and AFE3,
- in the second configuration Figure 37b, the DCT2 is instead connected to buses 3 and 4, regulated by AFE 3 and AFE4.

As already mentioned/presented, the DCT operates in open loop. Therefore, power flow transferred from one DC bus to another is dictated by the dc bus voltages, controlled by the AFEs. In steady-state, constant power is being transferred from one bus to another bus due to voltage difference between the two DC bus voltages. Forward and backward operation of DCT is possible because the DCT exhibits a bidirectional capability. In configuration 1, by convention, forward operation occurs when power is being transferred from bus 2 to 3 and in configuration 2, it occurs when the power is being transferred from bus 3 to 4.

In Figure 38, the DC voltages and AFE powers and currents are presented during operation

Figure 37: Configuration of the microgrid for operation of one DCT with two AFEs regulating the DC voltage (a) Configuration 1a: AFE2 - DCT1 - AFE3 (b) Configuration 1b: AFE3 - DCT2 - AFE4.

of the DCT, at steady-state, during voltage drop and during power reversal. For simplicity of notation, the subscripts 1 and 2 have been used to denote the primary and secondary side variables of the DCT (regardless of which DC-bus lines are connected to it).

(a)

(b)

Figure 38: Operation of the DC microgrid in (a) Configuration 1a (b) Configuration 1b
 (a) DCT1 in steady state backward operation (-21kW) during [0s,0.65s], power reversal during [2s,2.6s], steady state forward operation (+21kW) during [12s,14s];
 (b) DCT2 in steady state backward operation (-15kW) during [0s,0.75s], power reversal during [1.5s,2s], steady state forward operation (+23kW) during [12s,14s].

Looking at Figure 38a, the DCT1 is initially in backward operation with a steady-state power flow of -21 kW during the interval $[0\text{ s}, 0.65\text{ s}]$. Similarly, in Figure 38b the DCT2 is in backward operation with a steady-state power flow of -15 kW during the interval $[0\text{ s}, 0.75\text{ s}]$.

The DC bus voltages are regulated by the AFEs, and by changing the voltages references, the DC bus voltages slowly transition to the new setpoints and the DCT power varies with it. As presented in Figure 38a and Figure 38b, at 0.65 s and 0.75 s , a new voltage setpoint is given to AFE2 and AFE3, respectively (i.e., to the AFE connected on the primary side of the DCT).

During the initial transient, a voltage step is then occurring on both DC buses, which are coupled by the DCT itself. In this initial interval, the voltage difference between the two buses remains almost unchanged, and the power remains constant as well. Then, both DC voltages are slowly changed: the primary-side voltage increases towards the new setpoint, while the secondary-side voltage decreases to its initial value and, consequently, the power flow is reduced.

As the new voltage reference inverts the voltage difference, power reversal occurs. In Figure 38a, in the interval $[2\text{ s}, 2.6\text{ s}]$, a power reversal is occurring as the DCT transitions from backward to forward operation. In Figure 38b, similar power reversal occurs in $[1.5\text{ s}, 2\text{ s}]$.

After the power reversal, the DC bus voltages are then slowly regulated to their setpoint, and the power flow through the DCT reaches a new steady-state in forward operation. In Figure 38a, during the interval $[12\text{ s}, 14\text{ s}]$, the transient can be considered to be concluded and the DCT1 is operating in forward operation with a steady-state power flow of 21 kW. Similarly, in Figure 38b, during the interval $[12\text{ s}, 14\text{ s}]$, the DCT2 is operating in forward operation with a steady-state power flow of 23 kW.

In addition to that, in Figure 39, the DCTs voltages and currents are presented at steady-state, both in forward and in backward operation.

As can be seen in Figure 39, it is noticeable that the DCTs (which, as previously explained, are realized as LLC converters) operate slightly below the resonant frequency - as expected.

In Figure 40, power reversal is presented again, this time illustrating in detail both transitions from backward to forward operation (Figure 40a) and from forward to backward operation (Figure 40b), to give emphasis to the idle mode feature implemented in DCT2. In this case, when the power drops below 1 kW, the DCT active stage stops switching, and when the voltage difference between the two DC buses overcomes the threshold of 5 V , the DCT active stage starts switching again.

In both Figure 40a and Figure 40b, the idle mode can be seen from around 0.09 s until around 0.13 s , where the power stage is reactivated and power is being processed again.

6.2 Demonstration of two DCTs operating in the dc microgrid

In the configuration 1a and 1b, it has been verified that one DCT can interface two DC buses, whose voltages are regulated by AFE units. In what follows, results of two DCTs interfacing three DC buses are presented. The grid configuration is presented in Figure 41, where DCT1 is connected to DC buses 2 and 3 and DCT2 is connected to DC buses 3 and 4.

The test performed consists in dropping the voltage in bus 3 from the nominal value of 750 V to

Figure 39: Experimental waveforms of steady-state forward (top) and backward (bottom) operation of:
 (a) DCT1, with turn-off current of $I_{m,off} = 18$ A operating at $P = 20$ kW;
 (b) DCT2, with turn-off current of $I_{m,off} = 16$ A operating at $P = 40$ kW.

740 V. By doing so, power will be transferred simultaneously from DC buses 2 and 4 to DC bus 3 due to the simultaneous operation of both DCTs.

The results are shown in Figure 42. First, all powers are 0, since the three DC bus voltages are all set at 750 V. At the instant 0.7 s, the voltage reference of bus 3 is set to 740 V. Initially, all DC bus voltages experience a similar voltage drop, due to the coupling effect through the DCTs. Then, the DC voltages of bus 2 and bus 4 are kept back to their initial setpoint value of 750 V, while the DC voltage of bus 3 reaches the new setpoint of 740 V. As the voltage difference increases, the power across both DCTs increases to settle to around 21 kW for both DCTs. Consequently, the power flowing to bus 3, given by the sum of the contributions coming from both DCTs, settles around 42 kW.

(a)

(b)

Figure 40: Experimental waveforms of the power reversal and idle mode of DCT2 according to the voltage change of AFEs. Validation of the power reversal and idle mode operation with the DC grid. Grid is configured in Configuration 1b (a) transition from backward to forward operation; (b) transition from forward to backward operation.

Figure 41: Configuration of the microgrid for operation of two DCTs with three AFEs regulating the DC bus voltages.

Figure 42: Operation of the DC microgrid in Configuration 2 with 3 AFEs with 2 DCTs.

7 AC Grid Stability

In a power electronics dominated system, the stability is a key problem to be analyzed and verified. Different converters must coexist in the same network, and their mutual interaction must be investigated to allow for a stable and reliable operation. This becomes especially relevant for a hybrid AC/DC microgrid, where the converters interact on both the AC side and on the DC side through the corresponding networks.

7.1 Overview - Need for Stability Analysis

The AC grid stability is dependent on the interaction between each converter and the AC grid. A converter controller ill-tuning or a grid line too long can disrupt the overall grid stability, resulting in high harmonic power content across the grid and hampering the grid operation.

To illustrate the instability problem caused by the interactions of the converter and the grid, a simple example is given in the following. For this example, converter parameters and grid impedances have been changed to showcase both stable and unstable operations.

Three grid impedances have selected to create three scenarios as presented in Table 7, from null impedances (i.e., strong grid) to very large impedances values (i.e., weak grid).

Two converter parameters are modified and compared: type of filter (L- or LCL-filter) and type of GCC (PR-based controller in the $\alpha\beta$ -frame or PI-based controller in the dq -frame).

In Figure 43, the two types of filters are compared when a reactive power reference step is applied to the converter in the case of the three scenarios previously described in Table 7. As it can be seen, the AFE with an LCL-filter performs slightly better as the magnitude of the ripples in Scenario 2 and 3 are lower. However, both exhibits unstable behaviour in Scenario 3. Secondly, when applying the same reactive power step is applied to an AFE with a PR or a PI regulator as a GCC, as seen in Figure 44, the AFE with the PI regulator performs better as the system remains stable in all three examined scenarios.

From the previous examples it can be concluded that it is of primary importance to analyze the converter/grid interaction and provide design guidelines for the converter design and controller tuning. In this section, the system identification concept is presented and some guidelines are provided in the design of the AFE converters. In addition to that, a grid impedance measurement method is presented.

Table 7: Grid Impedance choices.

Scenario	R_g	L_g
Scenario n.1	0 Ω	0 H
Scenario n.2	1 Ω	9 mH
Scenario n.3	1.2 Ω	10.8 mH

7.2 Grid and converter interaction through the immittance approach

The converter/grid interaction can be studied through a small-signal analysis in the Laplace domain, based on the converter ac equivalent admittance and the ac grid equivalent impedance.

Considering a simple case where a converter is connected to an AC grid by a three-phase line, as presented in Figure 45a, the AC grid can be represented using a Thevenin equivalent model, as an ideal three-phase AC voltage source with a line with a given impedance matrix Z_g .

The converter, on the other hand, can be modelled as a Norton equivalent model, as an AC current source in parallel with an equivalent admittance matrix Y_c , as represented in Figure 45b. This admittance matrix is the result of both the converter hardware specifications (AC filter type and values) and of the controller design choices (controller type, gain values...).

The voltages at the point of common coupling V_{PCC} can be computed as:

$$V_{PCC} = (Z_g \cdot Y_c + I)^{-1} \cdot V_g \quad (3)$$

where V_{PCC} is a vector consisting of the voltages at the point of common coupling, Z_g is the grid impedance matrix, Y_c is the converter ac admittance matrix and V_g is the vector of the grid

Figure 43: q -axis current reference $I_{c,q}^{REF} = 0 A$ step from to $I_{c,q}^{REF} = 30 A$, corresponding to a Reactive Power step from $Q = 0 \text{ VAr}$ to $Q = 14.6 \text{ kVAr}$, obtained in simulation for different values of grid impedance $R_g = [0 \Omega, 1 \Omega, 1.2 \Omega]$. (a) LCL Filter; (b) L Filter.

Figure 44: q -axis current reference $I_{c,q}^{REF} = 0 A$ step from to $I_{c,q}^{REF} = 30 A$, corresponding to a Reactive Power step from $Q = 0 \text{ VAr}$ to $Q = 14.6 \text{ kVAr}$, obtained in simulation for different values of grid impedance $R_g = [0 \Omega, 1 \Omega, 1.2 \Omega]$. (a) PR controller; (b) PI controller.

voltages.

The stability of the grid-converter system is therefore dependent on the product $Z_g \cdot Y_c$, also called the minor loop gain, and the stability can be assessed by using a Generalized Nyquist Criterion (GNC), a Nyquist criterion adapted for the MIMO systems to the minor loop gain (MAcFARLANE & POSTLETHWAITE, 1977).

In order to apply the GNC and, hence, assess the stability, the knowledge of the converter ac equivalent admittance and of the AC grid equivalent impedance is necessary.

The converter ac admittance can be derived and computed precisely, assuming good knowledge of both its hardware and control parameters. In (Suntio, Messo, & Puukko, 2018), a model of the AFE converter is derived in the dq reference frame, and the converter admittance matrix

Figure 45: (a) AFE in the grid (b); Impedance representation in the AC side.

Y_c is written as:

$$Y_c(s) = \begin{bmatrix} Y_{c,dd}(s) & Y_{c,qd}(s) \\ Y_{c,dq}(s) & Y_{c,qq}(s) \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

In this report, the model has been adapted for the AFE unit previously described in Section 3, considering a GCC using a PR regulator in the $\alpha\beta$ frame. The frequency response of the admittance matrix is presented in Figure 46 for different steady-state operating points.

On the other hand, the equivalent impedance of the AC grid is typically unknown, and potentially varying in time. This is of special interests in case of reconfiguration of the AC microgrid. Moreover, the effect of other conversion structures connected to the same network may also influence the equivalent impedance seen by the AFE at the point of common coupling. Hence, it is necessary to develop methods to measure the grid impedance, precisely and fast.

7.3 Grid Impedance Estimation

In order to identify an impedance in the frequency spectrum, a perturbation current signal $i_P(j\omega)$ can be injected into the system, and by acquiring the voltage response $v_P(j\omega)$, the impedance can be reconstructed as:

$$Z(j\omega) = \frac{v_P(j\omega)}{i_P(j\omega)} \quad (5)$$

For a three-phase system, this operation should be done for all the terms of the equivalent impedance matrix Z_g . In the case of a grid impedance, the current signal must be added to the 50 Hz grid current at the PCC. This operation is typically and conveniently done in the dq reference frame, where small-signal perturbations are more easily superimposed over constant steady-state variables.

7.3.1 Perturbation and Acquisition Equipment

Perturbation injection systems must be employed to excite the system and allow the estimation of the grid impedances. Some methods rely on the grid existing commutating devices, switched loads for instance that would at turn-on or turn-off, generate signals of rich harmonic content [SOURCE]. Existing high-power, low-frequency, hard-switched power converters such as 12-pulse rectifiers (Robert et al., 1997) (Czarnecki & Staroszczyk, 1996) are also used. However, those methods rely on the grid behaviour and grid impedance estimation relies on the operation and location of those devices.

In order to master the time and location of the perturbation injection, dedicated harmonic generating devices (HGDs) are used (Czarnecki & Staroszczyk, 1996). Similarly to the commutating devices principle, a capacitor bank connected to the grid by a contactor generating a large current impulse is employed (Czarnecki & Staroszczyk, 1996). Those methods (Palethorpe, Sumner, & Thomas, 2000) (Sumner, Palethorpe, Thomas, Zanchetta, & Di Piazza, 2002) relying on signal impulses to evaluate the system impedance are called transient methods and they require signal injection of large magnitude, requiring high power devices capable of sustaining such current and voltage spikes. Furthermore, those large signal perturbation can affect the grid operation.

To cope with the defects of the transient methods, the so-called steady-state methods injecting low-power, low-magnitude signals have been developed. They rely on dedicated low power perturbation injection converters (PIC), that can generate perturbations of desired shape, magnitude and harmonic content (Tsukamoto, Ogawa, Natsuda, Minowa, & Nishimura, 2000; Knop

(a)

(b)

Figure 46: Frequency response of the equivalent admittance matrix Y_c of the AFE, in the dq -frame with: (a) an L Filter; and (b) an LCL filter, considering different power flows.

& Fuchs, 2009). Those devices still remain additional hardware that would need to be deployed in an existing grid.

Furthermore, as the PCC is located at the output of a converter, and the converter has typically a relatively large control bandwidth, it is possible to use the converter itself to generate perturbations up to a relatively large frequency range. Integrating the perturbation injection function in the AFE is therefore reducing the quantity of hardware to be installed.

Since the AFE adopted in this project, as described in Section 3, does not feature grid current sensors, it can be used as a perturbation injection equipment, but it cannot be employed as an acquisition device. Therefore, a dedicated measurement unit has to be employed, that would measure voltages and currents and reconstruct the grid impedance. The structure of the new system with the AFE, the grid and the measurement unit in between is presented in the scheme of Figure 47.

To inject a perturbation using the AFE as the source, the perturbation signal can be inserted in various points of the controller stages. It can be added to the controller voltage references that would be fed to the PWM, to the current references or at the DC-bus voltage reference.

In this report, for simplicity of implementation, it has been decided to insert the perturbation signal to the current references of the GCC.

7.3.2 Perturbation Signals

Multiple types of perturbation signals can be used to excite the system. The most important and used ones are:

- Single tone perturbation signals, where the perturbation is a sinusoidal signal of fixed frequency (Knop & Fuchs, 2009);
- Chirp signals, which are sinusoidal signals where the frequency is increased linearly, as presented in Figure 48a (Shen et al., 2013);

Figure 47: Scheme of a grid impedance measurement system with an AC grid of unknown impedance Z_g , an AFE as interlinking converter and perturbation injection source and a dedicated impedance measurement unit.

- Multitone signals, constructed as a superposition of multiple sinusoidal signals of fixed frequency, as in Figure 48c (Jaksic et al., 2015);
- Pseudo-Random Binary Sequence (PRBS) signals, which are square wave signals where the transition instants are defined by a pseudo-random binary sequence method, as graphically depicted in in Figure 48f (Martin, Nam, Siegers, & Santi, 2013).

Those signals, by their shapes, have many differences in terms of accuracy and speed performances.

In terms of frequency content, the single tone and multitone signals have a fixed number of frequencies, while the chirp and PRBS have a continuous frequency content up to their maximum bandwidth. In the case of the chirp signal, this bandwidth is determined by the frequency rate and by the duration of the injection, while for the PRBS the bandwidth is limited to the maximum switching time of the PRBS function.

In terms of signal duration, in the case of the multitone and PRBS signal, the signal duration is limited only by the minimum frequency. However, in the case of the chirp signal, it depends both on the minimum frequency, that will determine the frequency rate, and by the maximum frequency.

In terms of amplitude content per frequency, chirp and PRBS signals have similar amplitude content. In the case of the multitone signal, the amplitude is inversely proportional to the number of frequencies, thus limiting the use of the multitone method.

So in conclusion, the PRBS signal offers benefits of both the multitone signal, small signal

Figure 48: perturbation signals examples: Chirp signal: (a) time; (b) frequency, Multitone signal (c) time; (d) frequency, PRBS: (e) time; (f) frequency.

duration, and chirp signal, large and continuous frequency content, without any of their disadvantages, making this type of signal very popular for impedance measurement.

7.3.3 Numerical Results

To validate that the AFE can be effectively exploited to inject a perturbation signal useful to estimate the ac grid impedance, some preliminary measurements have been performed in simulation in the PLECS environment, where the AFE, the AC grid and IMU have been modelled.

(a)

(b)

Figure 49: PLECS model for grid impedance measurement with an AFE as a perturbation injection device - only sections related to for impedance measurement are presented: (a) AFE power stage connected to the AC grid (simulated as a 3 phases voltage source with a grid impedance); (b) Impedance measurement with extraction of the dq components of the currents and voltages.

Table 8: Grid Impedance choices for impedance estimation.

	L	R
$Z_{g,1}$	300 μH	33 $\text{m}\Omega$
$Z_{g,2}$	600 μH	66 $\text{m}\Omega$
$Z_{g,3}$	150 μH	16.5 $\text{m}\Omega$

The grid impedance (to be estimated), has been emulated as a simple resistive-inductive line, with different values that can be found in Table 8 (values close to the parameters of the AFE AC filter). The goal is determine the impedance in the dq frame, whose analytical expression is:

$$Z_g(j\omega) = \begin{bmatrix} Z_{g,dd}(j\omega) & Z_{g,qd}(j\omega) \\ Z_{g,dq}(j\omega) & Z_{g,qq}(j\omega) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} R_g + j\omega L_g & -\omega L_g \\ \omega L_g & R_g + j\omega L_g \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

For this grid model, $Z_{g,dd}(j\omega) = Z_{g,qq}(j\omega)$. Furthermore, at high frequencies, the grid impedance is mainly inductive and, therefore, the cross-coupling terms $Z_{g,qd}$, $Z_{g,dq}$ do not contain additional information compared to the direct terms ($Z_{g,dd}$, $Z_{g,qq}$). Therefore, for this example, by measuring the grid impedance solely in the d -axis ($Z_{g,dd}$), it is possible to extract the full information about the whole grid impedance matrix Z_g .

The perturbation signal has been injected solely on the current d -axis reference. Multiple single tone perturbation signals have been used, ranging from 25 Hz to 3.5 kHz and setting the current amplitude to 5 A. The impedance measurement unit acquires the grid voltages and currents and extracts the d -axis components to compute $Z_{g,dd}$:

$$Z_{g,dd}(j\omega) = \frac{v_{g,d}(j\omega)}{i_{g,d}(j\omega)} \quad (7)$$

The reconstructed grid impedances are compared to the theoretical values of Equation (6). The results have been reported in Figure 50. As can be seen, the estimated frequency response is very close to the theoretical values, and they are almost perfectly matching above 125 Hz.

Future works will be done to further explore AC grid estimation techniques (in generalized scenarios) and to experimentally validate the approach using the AFE equipment described in Section 3.

Figure 50: Comparison of the theoretical and measured impedance magnitude of (a) $Z_{g,1}$; (b) $Z_{g,2}$ and (c) $Z_{g,3}$ in simulation using the AFE as perturbation device and single tone perturbation injection signals.

8 Conclusions

This deliverable has presented the realization and testing of the main components of the microgrid realized for the Swiss demonstrator of the HYPERRIDE project by the Power Electronics Laboratory (PEL) of the École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL).

After a brief introduction on the hybrid AC/DC microgrid (Section 2.1), this report has been focused on describing in detail the structure, features, commissioning and testing of the main conversion structures of the network, being the Active Front End (AFE - Section 3) and the Direct Current Transformer (DCT - Section 4) units. It has been shown and verified that they are completely functional in all the required features, and that they can coexist in the same network (Section 6), allowing control of the power flow from the AC grid to the DC grid, and among different lines of the DC grid itself.

A brief discussion has also been given regarding the Photovoltaic (PV) emulator units (Section 5) and regarding the stability analysis at the AC/DC interface (Section 7).

Through the results of this work, the DC microgrid of the Swiss demonstrator is functional and ready to be tested in different operating conditions and configuration scenarios.

Future works will be done both to enhance and expand the DC microgrid, and to analyze the interoperability of different equipment into it. First, the interconnection of the PV emulators in the microgrid will be tested and verified. Then, the Dual Active Bridge (DAB) converter unit and the supercapacitor (SC) unit will be realized, commissioned, tested and integrated into the DC microgrid. Finally, further analysis will be done regarding the stability of the network in different operating conditions, considering also the DC network stability and enriching the AC grid impedance estimation techniques.

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